

WHICH IS THE MOST EFFECTIVE METHOD GTM OR CLT?**Maftuna Jumabayeva**

undergraduate student of Navoi State Pedagogical Institute

Babakhandova Nursila

undergraduate student of Navoi State Pedagogical Institute

Yugay Evgeniya Viktorovna

a scientific adviser, a senior teacher of Navoi State Pedagogical Institute

Abstract: This scientific article focuses on the ways of teaching English language. Also compares the difference between these methods and says about main principles of methods. As you know the methods provides a better basis to learn L2 language, as well teaching vocabulary, grammar and so on. By using the right and appropriate methods teacher can motivate and encourage students to learn English. But however, in my opinion the question «which method is the most appropriate for teaching a second language « is still under debate.

Аннотация: Данная научная статья посвящена способам обучения английскому языку. Также сравнивает разницу между этими методами и говорит об основных принципах методов. Как вы знаете, эти методы обеспечивают лучшую основу для изучения языка L2, а также для обучения лексике, грамматике и так далее. Используя правильные и подходящие методы, учитель может мотивировать и поощрять учащихся к изучению английского языка. Но, однако, на мой взгляд, вопрос «какой метод является наиболее подходящим для обучения второму языку» до сих пор остается дискуссионным.

Key words: communicative approach, traditional, principles, foreign languages, material, vocabulary.

Ключевые слова: Коммуникативный подход, традиционный, принципы, иностранные языки, материал, лексика,

INTRODUCTION

Why do you teach?

How do you teach?**Why do you teach the way you teach?**

The last question is probably the hardest to explain, maybe even to yourself.

Is it because that's how you were taught? Is it because that's how you were taught to teach? Or is it for some other reason?

Have you ever sat down and seriously thought about why you teach reading, writing, speaking, listening and culture the way you do?

If not, now is the time! And here's why: If you know the history

of *how* your subject has been taught, you’ll be able to choose the best methodological approach to teach your own students.

So let’s get started with the main foreign language methodologies, and then consider how to choose the best for your particular classroom.

METHOD AND MATERIAL

The communicative method is by far the most effective way to learn English today¹³. It appeared abroad around the 60s of the last century, and came to our country around the mid-90s. The communicative technique is focused precisely on the possibility of communication. Of the four «pillars» on which any language training is based (reading, writing, speaking and listening comprehension), increased attention is paid to the last two. The communicative method is designed primarily to remove the fear of communication. As you know, the goal of teaching a foreign language is the practical knowledge of the language, the assimilation of the language system and the acquisition of language skills. However, experience shows that often after graduation, even the best students do not have the skills of spontaneous speech, their vocabulary is poor and the grammatical structures are uniform in design. At present, the so-called communicative method of language acquisition is also widely used. The communicative approach to language learning is not at all a new method abroad; to complain that everyone understands, but they cannot speak. Since then, the communicative technique has changed significantly and has become widespread all over the world. Initially, it involved group classes with a native speaker. From the very first lesson, teaching was conducted in English. Later, the approach has undergone some changes and is now used both in a group and in individual classes.

A lot has been said and written about its effectiveness. Results are achieved by minimizing the use of the native language of the student during the classes. With this approach, it is very important to teach a person to think in a foreign language so that he perceives a foreign speech without any association with his native language. With this method of teaching the study of theoretical aspects is reduced to a minimum or is completely absent, and the main attention is paid to live communication, i.e., colloquial speech time is devoted to both vocabulary and grammar, however, their development is not the main goal of learning a foreign language. Speaking about the teaching materials used in the communicative teaching of a foreign language, it should be noted their almost unlimited variety. Teaching materials play a paramount role in stimulating the communicative use of the language. Traditionally, there are three main types of teaching materials based on the text based on the communicative task realities. Communicative methodology

The traditional method of learning English is also called grammar-translation. It consists in the systematic study of grammatical material, phonetics, forms the skills

¹³ <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/kommunikativnyy-podhod-v-obuchenii-inostrannomu-yazyku-1>

of translation and reading. Students compose dialogues, memorize them, learn words by topic, retell texts, perform written grammar exercises. The main features of this approach are memorization of the material and thoroughness. The traditional method of learning English is also called grammatical translation. It consists in the systematic study of the grammatical material of phonetics forms translation and reading skills. Students compose dialogues, memorize them, learn words on topics, retell texts, perform written grammar exercises. The main features of this approach are memorization of the material and thoroughness. The traditional methodology is that in the process of work, students must master in a given volume all types of speech activity.

ANALYSIS

The main principles of the communicative methodology of teaching English:

- The student begins to speak English from the first lesson. Even those who learn a language from scratch, master a couple of dozen phrases in the first lesson. This allows you to quickly get used to the sound of speech, prevents the appearance or eliminates the language barriers.

- Accuracy and Fluency – competent and fluent speech. When learning a language using this technique, you will not have to choose between speaking fluently or speaking correctly. The speech will be fluent and competent at the same time.

- When teaching, only modern authentic manuals are used. The carefully crafted English-language textbooks contain exciting and, most importantly, practical material that you can use in your life.

- The teacher goes through three stages of learning with the student: engagement (involvement), study (study) and activation (activation – use). At the engagement stage, the teacher involves the student in the learning process: he initiates an exciting discussion, offers to discuss a picture, etc. At the study stage, the student is explained the grammatical topic and the use of new words and expressions, that is, they work to expand vocabulary and master grammar. At the stage of activation of knowledge, the student performs various exercises to consolidate new grammar and words. This may be a continuation of the discussion of the topic under study, but with the application of the acquired knowledge.

According to the grammar-translation method, the learning and teaching of languages consist of the following principles:

- Teachers must assert their authority, as their role is to transmit knowledge to learners and the learner’s native language is the medium for instruction. Very little teaching is done in the target language. It is an extremely teacher-centered method of teaching.

- Learners need to be able to read the literature written in the target language and

learn all the relevant vocabulary and grammar. Learners do not play any active role and there is little learner–learner interaction.

- Literary language is superior to the spoken language. Learning a language consists of being able to read and translate a text into and out of the target language. The main focus of teaching is to develop the learner’s ability to read, write, and translate. Teachers would not direct learner’s attention to the content of the text which is treated as a translation exercise. Reading of very complex classical texts begins early. To be able to communicate using the target language is not an important goal for learners.

- The focus is on accuracy and not fluency. The grammar is taught systematically (following a sequencing grammar syllabus) through explicit extensive and elaborated teaching of grammatical rules. The main assumption is that a second language is learned through the deduction of the grammatical properties of a target L2. When learners have developed a conscious and explicit representation of that language, they can apply this ability in the production of sentences through translation from one language to the other.

- Errors are corrected. If learners answer a question incorrectly, the teacher would select somebody else to give the correct answer and/or he/she replies directly.

- Learners should memorize vocabulary in the form of isolated word lists. Vocabulary in the target language is learned through translation from the native language

CONCLUSION

The methods above are more effective in learning new words, based on different other researches and on our research made in Uzbekistan. It is suggested that method helps students more to learn vocabulary, although from the findings it is not clearly understood the effectiveness of one method over the other. The best teachers make use of all possible methodologies and approaches at the appropriate time, for the appropriate activities, and for those students whose learning styles require that approach.

References:

1. Borisova I. L. (Cheboksary, Russia) Diversity of linguistic Language Social networks and their application in the study of foreign languages
 2. Brown, H.D. 2001: Principles of language learning and teaching. New Jersey. Prentice Hall Regents.
- Online reference:
3. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/kommunikativnyy-podhod-v-obuchenii-inostrannomu-yazyku-1>

